

Territorial and temporal variation in pro-poor growth across Latin America

Barbora FRLIČKOVÁ, Luis PINEDA SALAZAR, Jaromír HARMÁČEK

Abstract: *This paper investigates the territorial and temporal variation in pro-poor growth across 16 countries in Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) in four growth sub-episodes between 2001 and 2021. Drawing on the pro-poor growth framework, we examine how changes in income, poverty, and inequality have shaped the extent to which income growth benefited the poor. Using the most recent data from the World Bank's Poverty and Inequality Platform, we calculate pro-poor growth metrics for each country and growth episode. These growth spells are then classified using a novel, standardized typology of pro-poor growth, enabling us to identify spatial and temporal patterns across the region. Our results reveal significant reductions in poverty and inequality, alongside persistent heterogeneity across countries and over time. Overall, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of inclusive and pro-poor growth dynamics in the LAC region, and offers potential insights to inform equity-oriented development policies.*

Keywords: *pro-poor growth, Latin America, Caribbean, inequality, poverty*

Introduction

Persistent inequality has been a defining feature of Latin America and the Caribbean throughout most of its history (Lustig et al. 2013). The region's average Gini coefficient remains the highest in the world, making it the most unequal region globally. This persists despite economic development since the 2000s, which brought consistent income growth and a sharp decline in both poverty and inequality (Gasparini et al. 2007, Lustig et al. 2013).

The sustained reduction in both income poverty and inequality suggests that not only did mean incomes rise steadily across societies, but the incomes of the poor increased relatively more. This reflects a distributional bias favoring the poor during the growth process, often referred to in development literature as the *pro-poorness* of growth (Shepherd et al. 2016). As per Klasen (2008), by tilting the development process toward the poor, pro-poor growth (PPG) can maximize poverty reduction without compromising overall economic growth.

Our paper builds on the pro-poor growth approach to address the main objective of this study, which is to analyze territorial and temporal variations in pro-poor growth in Latin America and the Caribbean region from 2001 to 2021. The aim of the paper is to classify and compare countries' growth processes in terms of how much they benefited the poor, and to map how these patterns evolved across countries and over time. We address two main research questions: first, what were the changes in incomes, poverty, and inequality in the region over this period; and second, to what extent and in what ways these changes benefited the poor, i.e., how pro-poor this development was. More specifically, the paper classifies countries' growth processes based on the degree of pro-poorness and shows their territorial and temporal distribution in the region.

To achieve this, we work with survey data on income from the Poverty and Inequality Platform (World Bank 2024). From these aggregate data, we simulate income distributions for countries in the region for four subsequent growth spells over 2001-2021 (subject to data

availability). Using these simulations, we calculate a specific measure of pro-poor growth (namely the Rate of Pro-poor Growth, RPPG) for each country and spell. Then we classify the growth processes for each country and spell using a new, standardized classification of pro-poor growth (based on how pro-poor the growth was). Subsequently, we examine how the results vary across countries and over time.

The paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we provide a review of relevant literature on pro-poor growth, and a brief summary of the debate over the definition, identification and measurements. The following section focuses on the description of the data we work with, our methodological framework, and analytical steps that are implemented. In the subsequent section, we analyze the results and discuss our findings. The final section concludes.

Literature review

The fight against poverty has been dominated by the concept of growth for decades. According to this paradigm, poor countries have to grow to lift their populations' living standards out of poverty. This is because growth is supposed to be unequivocally good for the poor (Dollar and Kraay 2002, Dollar et al., 2016). As part of then-dominant development thinking, it was argued that the poor would benefit from growth even if the gains were at first directed mostly to the non-poor, or even rich (Kakwani and Pernia, 2000, Kakwani and Son 2003) – meaning that all types of growth were assumed to be appropriate for poverty reduction, regardless of their inequality dynamics (Dollar and Kraay 2002).

However, the transition from the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) implied also a shift to a more comprehensive concept of development (SDGF n.d.). The SDGs' commitment to "leave no one behind" is inconsistent with an inequality-increasing development (UNDP 2016). Moreover, it has been argued that the SDGs and the World Bank's poverty eradication targets will not be achieved by 2030, even with neutral distribution of growth gains (Shepherd et al. 2016). Therefore, vital importance has been given to a new focus, moving away from pure growth, towards a pro-poor growth approach (SDGF n.d.).

Pro-poor growth (PPG) has been defined, in broad terms, as the type of growth that enhances the welfare of the poor by enabling their active participation, and by allowing the poor to benefit significantly from economic activities (Kakwani and Pernia 2000, OECD 2007, IMF, OECD, UN, World Bank 2000). However, such a broad definition can imply a variety of scenarios in which the poor, even though absolutely benefiting from economic growth, might experience a worsening of their relative income position in society. And the opposite is also possible: the relative income position of the poor may improve when compared to the non-poor, even though both groups become poorer in absolute terms.

Therefore, a more nuanced approach to PPG is needed. A *weak absolute* definition focuses on the end result of the growth process, meaning that all growth which benefits the poor, effectively reducing poverty, is classified as pro-poor (Ravallion 2004, Ravallion and Chen 2003). This is the weakest definition of PPG. On the contrary, a *strong absolute* definition implies that growth is pro-poor only if the poor people receive larger *absolute* benefits from growth than the non-poor (Grosse et al. 2008, Klasen 2008). This means that the *differences* between the poor's and the non-poor's incomes decrease (*absolute inequality* falls), forming the strongest definition of PPG. In between the two, the *relative* approach to PPG emphasizes that the poor benefit *proportionally* more from growth than the non-poor, implying that the poor's *growth rate* is greater than the mean growth rate (Kakwani and Pernia 2000, McCulloh and Baulch 1999, Son 2004). According to this, growth is *relatively* pro-poor if there is a reduction in both poverty and *relative inequality*.

While some authors consider the weak absolute definition of pro-poor growth sufficient because poverty rates decline (Ravallion and Chen 2003), for some others it is rather useless

as it would classify most positive growth processes as pro-poor (Kakwani and Son 2003). Although the strong absolute definition is the only one that implies a reduction in absolute inequality (Lopez 2004), it is of limited use considering that this situation rarely occurs, particularly for generally positive growth processes (White and Anderson 2001). The relative definition of PPG can therefore be regarded as the most usable one that assumes reduction of (relative) inequality, as it implies an inherent distributional shift in favor of the poor (Ravallion 2004). For example, advocating for a more intuitive interpretation of PPG, McCulloh and Baulch (1999) argued that economic processes should be called pro-poor whenever inequality declines (and vice versa – they should be called anti-poor when inequality increases).

In this context it must be noted that these definitions of PPG are based on two underlying conditions: positive income growth (especially that of the poor), and/or a distributional change biased towards the poor. Whether growth is still pro-poor – or to what extent – when only one of the conditions is fulfilled, has been the debate between the relative or absolute approach (Klasen 2008). However, based on this idea, it is apparent that the changes in poverty can be decomposed into the changes in the mean income (growth effects), and changes in the income distribution (redistribution effects, or inequality effects). These ideas were mathematically formalized by Datt and Ravallion (1992), Kakwani (1993), and Kakwani (2000), which then led to operationalizations of quantitative indicators measuring pro-poor growth.

These indicators followed the divide between (weak) absolute and relative approaches to PPG as well. While some of them were intended to primarily address the issue of the weak absolute pro-poor growth (Kraay 2006, Ravallion and Chen, 2003), some others were focused more on the relative comparisons (Kakwani and Pernia 2000, Kakwani and Son 2003, Son 2004). Additionally, Kakwani and Son (2008) modified their original metric to account also for the possibility of strong absolute PPG. All of these most frequently used indicators have been compared in terms of their advantages and disadvantages (Deutsch and Silber 2011, Harmáček et al. 2016), and they have also been extensively applied in the literature to study the pro-poorness of growth in various countries globally.

For example, in the Asian context, Zaman et al. (2012) found that growth in Pakistan was anti-poor due to biased federal policies. Ali et al. (2017) noted urban areas of the country experienced pro-poor growth (2001-2012), while rural areas did not. Patel et al. (2019) emphasized agricultural productivity for rural poverty reduction in India, while Permadi (2018) found Indonesia's growth favored the rich. Frličková (2021) studied rural and urban Indonesia (1996-2019) and found that weak absolute pro-poor growth occurred in both, but differences existed. While early urban growth reduced inequality, later periods showed rising inequality with poverty reduction ("trickle-down" growth).

As for analyses focused on Africa, Harmáček et al. (2017) compared the performance of the PPG indicators on the case study of Eastern African countries. Harmáček and Frličková (2020) analyzed long-term PPG across the continent, having identified West and North Africa as the most pro-poor regions, while East Africa was the least pro-poor region. Ngakoli (2014) found Congo's urban growth was pro-rich, while Adeosun and Tabash (2022) indicated that growth in West Africa was absolutely pro-poor. In terms of causes of pro-poor growth, for example Epo and Baye (2012) studied determinants of wellbeing and poverty changes in Cameroon, and Fufa (2021) examined the factors of pro-poor growth and income share in Ethiopia.

Number of studies focused also investigating pro-poor growth in Latin America. Araar (2012) focused on Andean countries (Ecuador, Colombia, Peru, Bolivia, Venezuela, 2005-2010), finding generally pro-poor growth, though disrupted by the 2008 crisis. Particularly, the use of the Growth Incidence Curve (GIC; Ravallion and Chen 2003) in inequality-growth analyses in the region based on the CEDLAS (2014) data has become widely extended over the past decades (examples include Gasparini et al. 2007, Grosse et al. 2008, Gasparini et al. 2014, Iniguez-Montiel 2014, Ferreira et al. 2019).

It was also shown, however, that instead of pointing out to the differences among the PPG indicators, a unifying interpretation framework can be created to classify the pro-poor growth dynamics in a standardized and more consistent way (Harmáček 2019). In our paper, we want to apply this classification of PPG to assess the pro-poor growth in countries of Latin America (and the Caribbean), including its temporal aspect. To achieve this, we first calculate the *Rate of Pro-poor Growth* (Ravallion and Chen 2003) – a specific PPG indicator – for all our spells. Subsequently, we interpret the results vis-à-vis the unifying PPG classification (Harmáček 2019). This allows us to assess the pro-poor growth in individual countries and spells. To check the robustness of our results, we repeat these steps with a different indicator of pro-poor growth, the *Poverty Equivalent Growth Rate* (Kakwani and Son 2008).

The Rate of Pro-poor Growth (RPPG) can be interpreted as the mean growth rate of the poor – which needs to be distinguished from the growth rate in the mean income of the poor. The indicator is based on poverty changes given by the Watts poverty index (Watts 1968), which is arguably one of the theoretically strongest poverty measures: it satisfies all elementary theoretical axioms set for a poverty measure, and it has also the convenient property of being equally sensitive in all percentiles below the poverty line (Kraay 2006). The Poverty Equivalent Growth Rate (PEGR) is defined as the rate of growth that has the same effect on poverty as the actual growth rate, provided that the growth process had not been accompanied by any change in inequality (Kakwani and Son 2008). It is the rate of growth if everyone in the society had received the same proportional benefits of growth.

Data and methods

This section presents the methodological framework and data used to answer the main research questions of the paper. Growth is analyzed in four crude sub-periods (or growth spells) for each country, rather than in annual changes, to capture systematic dynamics instead of yearly variations. Additionally, lower frequency of observations helps to minimize potential measurement errors of data sources (Barro 2000, Lundberg and Squire 2003). The dataset is based on household survey microdata from the World Bank's Poverty and Inequality platform (World Bank 2024). Note that household survey methodologies are not uniform across the included countries and over time (see below), and therefore all comparisons based on this data will inevitably contain a degree of variability. The selection of countries and years was made to minimize any potential bias, although a trade-off between accuracy and coverage was unavoidable. After these selections, all collected data underwent the same consistent processing methods.

The scope of the present work is to analyze pro-poor growth in the income dimension of poverty. Consumption is often regarded as a better proxy for well-being, but almost all country-level surveys in Latin America are based on income questionnaires, and only a few include consumption/expenditure questions (Gasparini et al. 2007). All income and survey information contained in the dataset is nationally representative, except for Argentina (for which the survey covers only urban population – representing however more than 85% of the total population; CEDLAS, World Bank 2021). These surveys are known to have a consistent absence of the extremely wealthy (Gasparini et al. 2014), but this should not affect the current analysis nor its conclusions, because it relates to all countries and periods. Additionally, the pro-poor measures focus mostly on the poor population, and thus they should not be affected by such an absence.

Although national definitions of poverty incorporate inherent society features that might depict a better image of the poor, they also make comparisons across countries impossible. Therefore, we use the absolute international poverty line of \$6.85/day (in 2021 PPP) as the standard poverty definition for all countries in all periods (see below). This threshold, which is set by the World Bank to roughly reflect the national poverty lines of the upper middle-income countries (Jolliffe et al. 2022), successfully eliminates the variability across countries but entails an unavoidable arbitrariness in defining the poor (Grosse et al. 2008).

Data

The study covers the period from 2001 to 2021 for 15 Latin American Countries and 1 Caribbean country. Our original idea was to analyze four subsequent 5-year long growth spells (2001-2006, 2006-2011, 2011-2016, 2016-2021) for these countries, i.e., to create a balanced panel of data. However, as income or consumption household surveys are not conducted annually across Latin American countries, it was not possible to stick to our original intention. Additionally, this is complicated even further by the fact that there may be methodology breaks between subsequent surveys within individual countries, meaning that such surveys cannot be directly compared in one growth spell. We therefore had to assess the data availability individually for each country, and include the closest available data point (forming a consistent growth spells) to the pre-defined years above (i.e., 2001, 2006, 2011, 2016, and 2021) to have as balanced and as comparable data as possible.

Furthermore, for comparability reasons, no growth spell was allowed to be shorter than three years (i.e., the difference between the first and the last year of a spell must have been at least three years). Moreover, the difference to the pre-defined year was allowed to be no more than three years as well. As a consequence of these criteria, some growth spells are not available for some countries included in our analysis, as indicated in tab. 1 that shows the data points used for each country.

Tab. 1. Data points used in our study

Country	Spell 1	Spell 2	Spell 3	Spell 4
Argentina		2006-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
Bolivia	2001-2006	2006-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
Brazil	2001-2006	2006-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
Chile		2006-2011	2011-2015	2015-2020
Colombia	2002-2005	2008-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
Costa Rica	2001-2006	2006-2009	2011-2016	2016-2021
Dominican Rep.	2001-2004	2006-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
Ecuador	2003-2006	2007-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
Honduras	2001-2006	2006-2010	2011-2016	2016-2019
Mexico	2000-2006	2006-2010	2010-2014	2016-2020
Nicaragua		2005-2009	2009-2014	
Panama	2001-2006	2008-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
Peru		2006-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
Paraguay	2002-2006	2006-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
El Salvador	2001-2006	2006-2011	2011-2016	2016-2021
Uruguay		2006-2011	2011-2016	2016-2019

Source: Created by authors, based on data availability in the World Bank's Poverty and Inequality Platform (World Bank 2024)

As shown, there are in total six growth spells missing across four countries, meaning that from the total of 56 spells (16 countries and four sub-periods), we can analyze income, poverty and inequality (i.e., pro-poor growth) changes in 50 cases. Additionally, we could not have

included some other Latin American or Caribbean countries such as Venezuela, Surinam, Guyana, Guatemala or Belize that did not have enough data points available. However, the data that we analyzed represented approximately 96% of the total population of Latin American and the Caribbean (based on World Bank 2021).

All income distribution data used in this study was taken from the latest available edition of the World Bank's Poverty and Inequality Platform (World Bank 2024). This database is built directly from the national household surveys and includes, among others, aggregated distributional data on income reported in 2021 PPP\$. These distributional data were used for all countries and years, as stated in tab. 1 above.

In the data preparation phase, the aggregated distributional data (provided in Lorenz curves percentiles) for each individual country and year were disaggregated into a simulated income distribution (on an individual level). Based on these income distributions, we calculated measures of inequality, poverty, and the mean income for each country and year. We also computed proportional changes in these measures over the entire time periods for each individual country (snapshots of these results are presented in tables 4 and 5). Additionally, we calculated two pro-poor growth measures (RPPG, and PEGR) for all growth spells across all countries in our dataset (subject to data availability). All data processing steps, and calculations were carried out in Stata 15 (StataCorp 2017), and the disaggregation procedures and pro-poor growth estimations were done using the Distributive Analysis Stata Package [DASP 2.3], originally developed by Araar and Duclos (2007).

Methodology

As mentioned in the literature review section, several indicators have been used to operationalize and measure pro-poor growth. While some of these indicators are considered primarily relative (i.e., focusing more on the proportional benefits of growth between poor and non-poor people), some others are defined as absolute (i.e., mostly interested whether the incomes of the poor increase). Additionally, each indicator introduced its own interpretation of the results in terms of growth pro-poorness. However, Harmáček (2019) showed that after some rather minor adjustments, one common standardized interpretation framework can be applied to all of these indicators. This is because most of these indicators reflect the nexus of changes in incomes, poverty, and inequality. As a result, six scenarios of interrelated changes among these three concepts are most likely to occur in reality, as shown in tab. 2.

Tab. 2. *Classification of growth spells per changes in incomes, poverty, inequality*

Classification	Income of the poor	Mean income	Inequality	Poverty
(1) Strong PPG	Increase	Decline	Decline	Decline
(2) Relative PPG	Increase	Increase	Decline	Decline
(3) Trickle-down PPG	Increase	Increase	Increase	Decline
(4) Pro-poor decline	Decline	Decline	Decline	Increase
(5) Anti-poor decline	Decline	Decline	Increase	Increase
(6) Immiserizing growth	Decline	Increase	Increase	Increase

Source: Authors; classification approach following Harmáček (2019)

These six categories can be also linked to the three basic approaches to pro-poor growth, as introduced at the beginning of the paper. While the first category corresponds to the *strong absolute pro-poor growth*, category 2 satisfies the *relative pro-poor growth* conditions, and

category 3 the *weak absolute pro-poor growth*. Note also, that if a growth spell is assessed as strong PPG, then it also meets the conditions of the relative, as well as trickle-down PPG. Similarly, a relative PPG implies also a trickle-down growth. The other three categories are rather anti-poor in the sense that they always indicate an increase in poverty. However, category 4 may be considered pro-poor within the traditional relative approach, because the position of the poor relatively improves (inequality between the poor and the non-poor falls), despite the decline in the poor's income. Similarly, the immiserizing growth category can be considered the worst for the poor, as it fulfils the conditions of both pro-poor and anti-poor declines. In this sense, the categorization shown in tab. 2 could be understood as ordinal in terms of the effects on the poor: the first category with the highest benefits, and the sixth category with the strongest negative impacts.

This standardized classification of pro-poor growth can be applied almost on any pro-poor growth indicator (with some slight adjustments for some of them). This means that such a unified interpretation framework allows for a direct comparison of results obtained by various indicators of PPG. This is shown in tab. 3.

Tab. 3. PPG measures interpretation using the standardized classification of growth spells

Standardized classification of growth spells		Condition of statistical significance
1. Strong pro-poor growth	$PPG_measure > 0 > g$	$PPG_measure_lb > 0 > g_ub$
2. Relative pro-poor growth	$PPG_measure > g > 0$	$PPG_measure_lb > g_ub \wedge g_lb > 0$
3. Trickle-down growth	$g > PPG_measure > 0$	$g_lb > PPG_measure_ub \wedge PPG_measure_lb > 0$
4. Pro-poor decline	$0 > PPG_measure > g$	$0 > PPG_measure_ub \wedge PPG_measure_lb > g_ub$
5. Anti-poor decline	$0 > g > PPG_measure$	$0 > g_ub \wedge g_lb > PPG_measure_ub$
6. Immiserizing growth	$g > 0 > PPG_measure$	$g_lb > 0 > PPG_measure_ub$

Source: Authors, using a classification approach based on Harmáček (2019);

Notes: g is the growth rate of the mean income. $PPG_measure_lb$ and $PPG_measure_ub$ are the lower and upper bounds of the 95% confidence interval of any pro-poor growth measure's estimate, while g_lb and g_ub are the lower and upper bounds of the 95% confidence interval of the estimate of g . While this interpretation fully works for both indicators used in this paper, for some others slight adjustments would be needed.

For results to be statistically significant, it must hold that the confidence interval of a PPG measure's estimate does not overlap with the confidence interval of the estimate of g , and at the same time, none of the confidence intervals contains the value of zero. If any of these conditions is unmet, it is not possible to conclusively decide the category that a growth spell should fall into.

In this paper, we use our data to estimate two pro-poor growth measures (RPPG and PEGR) for the defined growth spells across countries in Latin America. We then apply the classification of pro-poor growth to these estimates to observe the territorial distribution of growth's pro-pooriness, as well its dynamics over time. Since the final classifications may slightly differ for the distinct PPG measures (because of the differing approaches to definitions and underlying indicators of poverty), we consider the results obtained on the basis of PEGR more as our robustness check to the main results acquired using RPPG.

Results

Income, poverty, and inequality

During the entire period under study (2001-2021), the majority of countries included in our analysis increased their (daily) mean income, and succeeded also in reducing poverty (as measured both by the poverty headcount ratio, and the Watts index) and inequality (as measured by the Gini index). More specifically, the poverty levels declined in all analyzed countries, and the same is true for inequality, although the reduction of the latter was less pronounced. While there was no decline in the daily mean incomes, some countries did not achieve a substantive growth, and faced a stagnation. This is especially the case for Argentina, Dominican Republic, Honduras, and Mexico (tab. 4).

Tab. 4. *Initial and final income, inequality and poverty levels in countries of the region*

Country	Survey Year	Gini index	Headcount ratio	Watts index	Daily mean income
Argentina	2006	0.4636	0.1681	0.0989	24.17
	2021	0.4202	0.1063	0.0497	24.77
Bolivia	2001	0.5743	0.5183	0.5696	11.46
	2021	0.4093	0.1515	0.0823	19.55
Brazil	2001	0.5845	0.4805	0.4210	13.87
	2021	0.5295	0.2837	0.1926	19.18
Chile	2006	0.4733	0.2999	0.1406	15.43
	2020	0.4493	0.0801	0.0376	25.49
Colombia	2002	0.5605	0.5773	0.4738	10.53
	2021	0.5153	0.3927	0.2876	14.16
Costa Rica	2001	0.5154	0.2812	0.2024	18.39
	2021	0.4869	0.1446	0.0676	25.18
Dominican Republic	2006	0.5198	0.4499	0.2792	13.00
	2021	0.3854	0.2315	0.0904	14.04
Ecuador	2003	0.5356	0.5779	0.4935	9.73
	2021	0.4581	0.3182	0.1726	14.68
Honduras	2001	0.5538	0.5650	0.5533	10.10
	2019	0.4818	0.4959	0.4055	10.12
Mexico	2000	0.5261	0.4812	0.3322	12.02
	2020	0.4542	0.3258	0.1683	13.97
Nicaragua	2005	0.4886	0.6102	0.4124	8.76
	2014	0.4618	0.4208	0.2257	11.72
Panama	2001	0.5677	0.4008	0.4511	15.78
	2021	0.5088	0.1292	0.0704	30.87
Peru	2006	0.5036	0.5587	0.4711	9.16
	2021	0.4027	0.3378	0.1680	12.09
Paraguay	2002	0.5728	0.5170	0.4220	12.04
	2021	0.4292	0.2103	0.0831	17.32
El Salvador	2001	0.5139	0.5242	0.4715	10.18
	2021	0.3902	0.2837	0.1585	13.02
Uruguay	2006	0.4596	0.2234	0.0879	18.90
	2019	0.3969	0.0504	0.0143	28.78

Source: Authors' calculations using data from the World Bank (2024);

Note: Calculations are based on the \$6.85 per day (2021 PPP\$) poverty line. The results are only illustrative since some of the income surveys for the initial and final years may not be fully comparable.

Since the data cover periods of varying lengths for individual countries, we annualized the changes in poverty, inequality, and the mean income to improve the cross-country comparability. Despite the overall positive patterns of development presented above, there were substantial differences across countries. For example, while Panama had annualized income growth of 4.78%, its Gini index declined only by 0.52% per annum. On the contrary, Dominican Republic had annualized growth of merely 0.53%, but experienced 1.72% per annum decrease in its Gini index. However, as a result of these changes, both countries achieved a similar annualized pace of headcount poverty rate reduction (3.24%, and 3.39%). The two best performing countries in annualized rate of poverty reduction were Uruguay, and Chile, while Honduras and Mexico would be ranked on the opposite end of this ladder. Tab. 5 contains the breakdown of the annualized changes in income, inequality and poverty indicators for individual countries.

Tab. 5. Income, inequality and poverty annualized changes in countries of the region

Country	Survey Year	Annualized changes in			
		Gini index	Headcount ratio	Watts index	Daily mean income
Argentina	2006-2021	-0.62%	-2.45%	-3.32%	0.17%
Bolivia	2001-2021	-1.44%	-3.54%	-4.28%	3.53%
Brazil	2001-2021	-0.47%	-2.05%	-2.71%	1.91%
Chile	2006-2020	-0.36%	-5.24%	-5.23%	4.66%
Colombia	2002-2021	-0.42%	-1.68%	-2.07%	1.81%
Costa Rica	2001-2021	-0.28%	-2.43%	-3.33%	1.85%
Dominican Republic	2006-2021	-1.72%	-3.24%	-4.51%	0.53%
Ecuador	2003-2021	-0.80%	-2.50%	-3.61%	2.83%
Honduras	2001-2019	-0.72%	-0.68%	-1.48%	0.01%
Mexico	2000-2020	-0.68%	-1.61%	-2.47%	0.81%
Nicaragua	2005-2014	-0.61%	-3.45%	-5.03%	3.75%
Panama	2001-2021	-0.52%	-3.39%	-4.22%	4.78%
Peru	2006-2021	-1.34%	-2.64%	-4.29%	2.13%
Paraguay	2002-2021	-1.32%	-3.12%	-4.23%	2.31%
El Salvador	2001-2021	-1.20%	-2.29%	-3.32%	1.39%
Uruguay	2006-2019	-1.05%	-5.96%	-6.44%	4.02%

Source: Authors' calculations using data from the World Bank (2024);

Note: Calculations are based on \$6.85 per day (2021 PPP\$) poverty line. The annualized changes are calculated by dividing the total change of a variable over the period by the years difference of that period. They do not correspond to average annual changes. The results are only illustrative since some of the income surveys for the initial and final years may not be fully comparable.

While promising patterns of income growth, and both inequality and poverty reductions are observed for the majority of countries, they do not necessarily imply that pro-poor growth occurred in societies across Latin America (and the Caribbean). Therefore, we firstly want to investigate how the benefits of growth were distributed between the poor and non-poor people in these societies, which should be done through an investigation of the disaggregate

changes. And second, we aim to analyze pro-poor growth in a more granular perspective, i.e., by examining a higher number of growth spells per individual countries. Therefore, the subsequent analysis focuses on the estimation of more specific pro-poor growth indicators to examine the nexus between income growth, inequality, and poverty changes in a more detailed way.

Pro-poor growth in Latin American countries

We calculated the RPPG for all available growth spells. We also calculated the growth rate in the mean income (g) for the identical spells since these are needed for interpretations of the individual pro-poor growth indicators' results. As a robustness check, we additionally estimated the PEGR for all our growth spells.

The RPPG was primarily designed as an indicator of (weak) absolute pro-poor growth, indicating its occurrence if $RPPG > 0$. It was also shown that if $RPPG > g$, then the distributional shifts favored the poor relatively more than the non-poor (Ravallion and Chen 2003). We carried out these analyses of (weak) absolute and relative pro-poor growth, and presented their results in tab. 6 and tab. 7. We found that the weak absolute pro-poor growth occurred in 49 cases out of the 58 growth spells – the prevalence was especially dominant in the second and third periods. These results are shown in tab. 6.

As for the relative assessment of pro-poor growth, the results in tab. 7 show that in 46 out of 58 spells, the income distributional shifts were in favor of the poor people, and this pro-poor development was most pronounced in the second period. Note, that the situation of pro-poor growth decline, in which the incomes of both the poor and non-poor decline with the poor being hit less, is also classified as the relative PPG category in this context.

Tab. 6. *Weak absolute assessment of pro-poor growth based on the RPPG*

Weak absolute assessment	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	TOTAL
Weak absolute PPG achieved	9	15	15	10	49
No weak absolute PPG	2	1	1	4	8
<i>Insignificant results</i>	0	0	0	1	1
TOTAL	11	16	16	15	58

Source: Authors' calculations using data from the World Bank (2024)

Tab. 7. *Relative assessment of pro-poor growth based on the RPPG*

Relative assessment	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	TOTAL
Relative PPG achieved	9	14	12	11	46
No relative PPG	2	2	4	3	11
<i>Insignificant results</i>	0	0	0	1	1
TOTAL	11	16	16	15	58

Source: Authors' calculations using data from the World Bank (2024)

A more nuanced categorization of the results is obtained on the basis of the classification of pro-poor growth, which was introduced in the methodology section. These results are summarized in tab. 8 and they reveal that growth was indeed benefiting the poor more than

the non-poor for the majority of the growth spells studied (in 42 out of 58 cases). However, much more details are available. For example, it is observed that in twelve of those cases, even the absolute inequality between the poor and the non-poor declined, meaning that the *difference* between incomes of the poor and the non-poor decreased. While such developments were certainly very positive for the poor, they were the consequences of general declines in the mean incomes, which is rather challenging for a society as whole.

Tab. 8. Standardized classification of growth spells

Growth spells classification	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	TOTAL
Strong PPG	1	3	2	6	12
Relative PPG	8	10	10	2	30
Trickle-down PPG	0	2	3	1	6
Pro-poor decline	0	1	0	2	3
Anti-poor decline	1	0	0	1	2
Immiserizing growth	1	0	0	0	1
<i>Insignificant results</i>	0	0	1	3	4
TOTAL	11	16	16	15	58

Source: Authors' calculations using data from the World Bank (2024)

In 30 additional growth spells – more than a half of those analyzed – growth processes benefited the poor *relatively* more than the non-poor, meaning that both poverty and *relative* inequality declined. Although these developments were *probably* less favorable to the poor (this could not be unambiguously assessed based on the measures used), they were on average positive for the rest of the society since mean incomes rose as well. These results suggest that in 72.5% (42) of all growth spells measured, the poor benefited from growth at least *relatively* more than the non-poor. In all of these spells, the incomes of the poor increased, which also happened for six more growth spells with the trickle-down growth. This means that in almost 83% of all spells, growth was pro-poor at least in the weak absolute sense (incomes of the poor grew).

On the contrary, only in six spells (10%), growth processes were unfavorable to the poor. In half of these cases, there was a general decline in the societies' mean incomes, but the poor were hit *relatively* less than the non-poor. While there was a reduction in (both *absolute and relative*) inequality between the poor and the non-poor, poverty increased as a consequence of the decline in income. This indicates that even though the gap between the poor and the non-poor shrank, the poor became poorer in absolute terms (their incomes decreased). In additional two spells, the poor were hit relatively more by the recession in the mean income. Both poverty and *relative* inequality between the poor and the non-poor increased, implying that the poor became worse off both in the weak absolute (lower incomes, higher poverty) and relative terms (higher inequality when compared to the non-poor). The most unfavorable development for the poor, immiserizing growth, occurred only once (in the first period in Honduras). While the society's mean income increased, the poor became more impoverished as their incomes declined. This led to a higher poverty, and an elevated levels of inequality (both *relative and absolute*) between the poor and the non-poor.

Fig. 1 shows the territorial variation of pro-poor growth over time in Latin America and the Caribbean. Although the relative pro-poor growth results prevail, it can be observed that there is a variation of results even within individual countries over time, and this especially holds for the regional powers such as Brazil and Mexico.

Fig. 1. Pro-poor growth in Latin American countries (2001-2021) based on the Rate of Pro-poor Growth (RPPG) indicator; Source: Authors' calculations using data from the World Bank (2024)

Lastly, as a robustness checks of our results, we recalculated all results using a different measure of pro-poor growth, the Poverty Equivalent Growth Rate (PEGR). As Fig. 2 and tab. 9

show, our results were largely confirmed. The main difference was that with PEGR, we obtained more spells assessed as statistically insignificant, particularly in the fourth period. Apart from this, however, the results remained similar even in terms of their geographical distribution, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Pro-poor growth in Latin American countries (2001-2021) based on the Poverty Equivalent Growth Rate (PEGR) indicator;
 Source: Authors' calculations using data from the World Bank (2024). Note: Incidence of poverty (Foster et al. 1984) was used as the underlying poverty indicator.

Tab. 9. Robustness checks results with PEGR as the pro-poor growth measure

Weak absolute assessment	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	TOTAL
Weak absolute PPG achieved	9	13	13	6	41
No weak absolute PPG	1	0	1	4	6
<i>Insignificant results</i>	1	3	2	5	11
TOTAL	11	16	16	15	58
Relative assessment	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	TOTAL
Relative PPG achieved	8	15	11	7	41
No relative PPG	2	1	3	2	8
<i>Insignificant results</i>	1	0	2	6	9
TOTAL	11	16	16	15	58
Growth spells classification	Period 1	Period 2	Period 3	Period 4	TOTAL
Strong PPG	0	1	0	2	3
Relative PPG	7	11	10	3	31
Trickle-down PPG	2	1	1	1	5
Pro-poor decline	0	0	0	1	1
Anti-poor decline	1	0	0	0	1
Immiserizing growth	0	0	1	0	1
<i>Insignificant results</i>	1	3	4	8	16
TOTAL	11	16	16	15	58

Source: Authors' calculations using data from the World Bank (2024);

Note: Incidence of poverty (Foster et al. 1984) used as the underlying poverty indicator

Discussion

Our results indicate that pro-poor trends generally prevailed across countries and over time in Latin America. In most growth spells, the poor saw their situation improve, and in many cases they improved faster than the non-poor. The standardized classification of pro-poor growth provides further detail on the nature of these gains, especially when they are compared to the rest of society. We also observed that the most pro-poor developments were concentrated in the first two sub-periods (especially the second), when distributional shifts tended to favor the poor. This aligns with the findings of Lustig et al. (2013), who documented sharp declines in poverty and inequality for a comparable group of Latin American countries over roughly the same timeframe.

The country trajectories illustrate how heterogeneous these dynamics are over time and across contexts. In Brazil, after two sub-periods of a very positive development, growth processes gradually weakened their benefits for the poor, turning into a trickle-down scenario in the third period, and even into a pro-poor decline in the fourth period. Similar development is observed in Mexico, where a pro-poor decline occurred in the second period, after a period of relative pro-poor growth. In the last period, Mexico experienced a situation of strong pro-poor growth, which is the most favorable for the poor (both absolute inequality and poverty decline), but not for the society as a whole as the mean income declines.

Another interesting story presents Honduras, which started off with the only case of immiserizing growth in our analysis, followed by a phase of the relative pro-poor growth, which is rather a positive setting for the society as a whole. However, the country subsequently

experienced two periods of strong pro-poor growth that generally benefits the poor people, but not the rest of the society. This actually mirrors the fact that Honduras' mean income stagnated over the entire 2001-2021 time period.

All of these examples show that there was a non-negligible variation in the results *within* individual Latin American countries over time. The only country with the same positive outcome over the entire period was Uruguay, which experienced relative pro-poor growth in each of the three periods (for which there were available data). Similarly, both Bolivia and Ecuador had three periods of relative pro-poor growth (and one insignificant result in which the growth process could not have been categorized), while Chile had two periods of relative pro-poor growth (and one insignificant result). In all other cases, countries experienced at least two different types of growth.

Tracking pro-poor growth within individual countries over time also helps show how differently development affects the poor. In Mexico, development processes changed drastically since the mid-1990s. At that time, according to Lustig et al. (2013), Mexico was characterized by high and increasing inequality. Moreover, Iniguez-Montiel (2014) found that during the period 1992-2000, the mean income fell by 0.2% per annum, mostly due to the Peso crisis. This especially affected the poor as the income of the bottom 20 percent of population decreased by an even larger (1.3% per year). This corresponds to broader regional trends, based on which Gasparini et al. (2007) described the 1990s as a disappointing decade. After this period, however, the pattern in Mexico changed, and from 2000 to 2008, the income of the bottom 20 percent grew by 3.7%, while the estimated mean income grew by barely 1.6% *per annum* (Iniguez-Montiel 2014). During the mid-1990s and mid-2000s the government spending patterns in Mexico became increasingly progressive, and their equalizing contribution was significant in all years (Lustig et al. 2013). Our result for 2002-2006 confirmed that Mexico's mean growth pattern, unlike in the previous period, benefited especially the poor. This positive development was interrupted in the second period (2006-2010), in which Mexico experienced a period of pro-poor decline. However, Mexico's poor benefited from growth in the next two periods as well.

Finally, our robustness check using PEGR supports the main story. Re-estimating all growth spells with PEGR produced broadly similar findings about the distributional patterns of growth. The main difference was that PEGR classified a higher number of spells as statistically insignificant, particularly in the fourth period, which indicates greater caution in attributing those changes specifically to pro-poor dynamics. Importantly, however, the key regional patterns and the country-level trajectories remained consistent, confirming the robustness of our main findings.

Conclusion

The "leave no one behind" principle of the SDGs shifted the development focus from broad economic growth to more inclusive patterns that benefit the poor. In this context, the concept of pro-poor growth gained importance even without a clear consensus on the exact definitions and measurements. In this paper, we used two existing and widely used measures (namely, the Rate of Pro-Poor Growth, and the Poverty Equivalent Growth Rate) and interpreted their results through an innovative classification to assess how growth benefited the poor in 16 countries of Latin America and the Caribbean in four consecutive growth spells over 2001-2021.

Over this period, Latin America, although it remains the most unequal region in the world, made substantial progress in both poverty and inequality reduction. The region's growth pattern from 2001 to 2021 was marked by a sharp decline in inequality and poverty, at least for the 16 countries included in this study. During the period under review, all countries experienced a reduction in inequality, and the incidence of poverty was reduced significantly as well.

Although there were more variations in performances, the mean incomes also increased for most countries included in the study, while it stagnated for some others.

Overall, the patterns of growth for countries across the region from 2001 to 2021 was found to be mostly pro-poor. Out of the total of 58 growth spells, 72.5% to 83% were classified as pro-poor (depending on the definition). Uruguay experienced relative pro-poor growth in all sub-periods, while Bolivia, Ecuador, and Chile had relative pro-poor growth in all spells with statistically significant results. Furthermore, only in 10% of all growth spells, growth processes were unambiguously unfavorable to the poor.

Finally, our results suggest that both the overall income growth and inequality reduction are key determinants to lower poverty rates across the region. Policy-wise, this should be a strong call to give further priority to inequality reducing policies as the path to achieving the SDGs. The remarkable inequality reduction that the region experienced was not only an accomplishment on its own, but it was also a vital key to the considerable reduction in poverty during the period.

Thus, recognizing the importance of poverty reducing strategies in the growth policies of countries in the regions is crucial to their success and sustainability. This takes a paramount importance when considering that low growth rates of income (such as those typically seen in the Latin American region) might be partly (or completely) overturned by an increase in inequality. Additionally, a growth pattern based solely on high growth rates that ignores the inequalities in the distribution of gains is inconsistent with the current SDG agenda.

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Authors' affiliations

Barbora FRLIČKOVÁ

Department of Development & Environmental Studies
Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc
17. listopadu 12, 771 46 Olomouc
Czech Republic
barbora.frlickova@upol.cz

Luis PINEDA SALAZAR

Department of Development & Environmental Studies
Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc
17. listopadu 12, 771 46 Olomouc
Czech Republic
pineda.luis.es@gmail.com

Jaromír HARMÁČEK

Department of Development & Environmental Studies
Faculty of Science, Palacký University Olomouc
17. listopadu 12, 771 46 Olomouc
Czech Republic
jaromir.harmacek@upol.cz